

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Instead of focusing on grammatical purity, the Communicative Approach emphasizes the ability to express the message's meaning. It first appeared in the 1960s and is still in use today. The strategy emphasizes genuine dialogue and negotiating meaning. Its primary feature is English language comprehension through engaged student involvement, including role-playing, games, and information gaps. Both verbal and written communication are covered by the concept of "communicative competence," which is the gradual development of the capacity to use a language for personal gain. The term "communicative competence" denotes a change in emphasis from the grammatical to the communicative aspects of the language, or the uses of language and the conversation process. The Communicative Approach places a strong emphasis on the notion that communication of meaningful content is necessary for success. When students engage in genuine communication, they will employ their natural strategies, which will help them learn how to use the language.*

Key words: *communicative competence, language acquisition, learning language, interaction, communicative purpose.*

As it's known, the purpose of teaching a foreign language is practical language proficiency, mastering the language system and acquiring language skills. However, often after graduation, even the best students do not have the skills of spontaneous speech, their poor vocabulary and the uniformity of the design of grammatical structures are felt.

Specially conducted studies have shown that more than 90% of foreign language classes are mainly aimed at teaching the language system, and not at mastering it. The main subject and the object of training with the traditional method is the teacher. He directs the types of speech activity, gives comments and organizes the learning process as a whole. At the same time, teaching methods and techniques are not aimed at the formation and development of students' speech skills and abilities.

The traditional method of learning English is also called grammar-translation. It consists of the systematic study of grammatical material, phonetics, forms translation and reading skills. Students compose dialogues, memorize them, learn words by topic, retell texts, perform written grammar exercises. The main features of this approach are memorization of the material and thoroughness. The peculiarity of the traditional methodology is that in the process of work, students must master all types of speech activity in a given volume.

Currently, the so-called communicative method of language acquisition is widely used. The communicative approach in language learning is not a new technique at all: it appeared abroad around the 60s of the last century, and came to our country around the mid-90s. Then all the English language learners began to complain that "they understand everything, but they can't speak."

The adherents of the communicative approach took the path of combating this discrepancy. Since then, the communicative methodology has been significantly transformed and it has received mass distribution all over the world. Initially, it assumed group classes with a native speaker. From the very first lesson, the training was conducted in English. Later, the approach underwent some changes, and now it is used both in a group and in individual classes. Much has been said and written about its effectiveness.

The results are achieved by minimizing the use of the learner's native language during classes. With this approach, it is very important to teach a person to think in a foreign language so that he perceives foreign speech without any associations with the native language. With this method of teaching, the study of theoretical aspects is

minimized or absent altogether, and the main attention is paid to live communication, i.e. conversational speech.

There is often a misconception that when using a communicative approach, the study of grammar is given inexcusably little time. In fact, in the learning process, a lot of attention and a sufficient amount of time is paid to both vocabulary and grammar, but their development is not the main goal of learning a foreign language. Speaking about the educational materials used in the communicative teaching of a foreign language, it should be noted their almost unlimited variety. Educational materials play a primary role in stimulating the communicative use of language.

Traditionally, there are three main types of educational materials: text-based, based on a communicative task, and realities grammar is present in a limited form as needed, vocabulary – as needed for practical tasks, practice – in the form of life situations. Discussion of real-life situations attracts students, arouses keen interest and a desire to share their ideas. The main place in the communicative teaching of a foreign language is occupied by game situations, work with a partner, tasks for finding mistakes, which not only allow you to increase your vocabulary, but also teach you to think analytically.

Many supporters of the communicative approach support the use of authentic materials in the classroom. These can be various linguistic realities, such as magazines, advertisements and newspapers, or visual sources around which communication can be built (maps, graphs, tables, etc.). The main task of the communicative methodology is to help the student get rid of the notorious language barrier. About 70% of the classes on the communicative methodology are devoted to conversational practice on various topics. And yet it would be a mistake to assume that the communicative approach is exclusively conversations in English.

The communicative approach is designed to develop oral and written speech, vocabulary, grammar, listening and reading skills. The teacher goes with the student three stages of training: engagement (involvement), study (study) and activation (activation – use). At the engagement stage, the teacher engages the student in the

learning process: initiates an exciting discussion, offers to discuss a picture, a problem, a film, etc.

At the learning stage, the student is explained the grammatical topic and the use of new words and expressions, that is, they work on expanding the vocabulary and mastering grammar. At the stage of knowledge activation, the student performs various exercises for fixing new grammar and words. This may be a continuation of the discussion of the topic under study, but with the application of the knowledge gained. Like any other way of learning a language, the communicative approach has transformed over time, but its fundamental principles have not changed. These include the following:

1. The student begins to speak English from the first lesson. Even those who study the language from scratch, master a couple dozen phrases in the first lesson. This allows you to quickly get used to the sound of speech, prevents the appearance of a language barrier or gets rid of it.

2. When learning a language using this method, you do not need to choose: speak fluently or speak correctly. The task is to make the speech fluent and literate at the same time. Modern authentic manuals are used in the training.

Carefully crafted English-language texts contain fascinating practical material that can be used in life and in professional activities. The ability to speak competently is the main skill, over improvement which the communicative technique works. Students are taught not only to speak on different topics, but also to monitor the correctness of speech. It's not secret that the language barrier often develops from the fact that a person is afraid to make a mistake in a conversation. And the communicative approach successfully combats this fear: up to 70% of the lesson time is devoted to the development of speaking skills.

Communicative approach helps to remove both the language and psychological barrier directly: students lose the fear of speaking in English. The more and more often a student speaks English, the faster he learns to formulate his thoughts. And in classes using a communicative technique, students talk most of the lesson. The teacher builds a dialogue in such a way that it is interesting for students

to answer questions and they can use their knowledge to the maximum. The communicative method teaches coherent speech, various colloquial phrases and cliches that allow you to speak fluently afterwards. Students learn not only to hear, but also to understand English. In the classroom, students listen to and analyze small audio and video materials together with the teacher. Usually, such material is used as a basis for discussion.

The communicative method of teaching English is aimed at developing the ability to speak spontaneously on various topics. In the classroom, only the language being studied is mainly used. The teacher sometimes explains complex nuances in Russian, but 90% of the lesson is conducted in English. This technique allows not only to "rebuild" to use English, but also to stop mentally translating Russian phrases into English and vice versa. Grammar and vocabulary are studied for communication, not "for show".

The communicative methodology assumes a very correct and simple principle of studying grammatical constructions: no one crams theory. The teacher explains this or that rule and together with the students begins to work it out in practice, bringing the skill of its use to automatism. They do the same with new words: no cramming, only repeated practical application.

Recently, it has become fashionable to talk about how children learn their native language in order to try to copy this process when learning a foreign language. Remember how children learn the language: they speak first, and already in the process of communication adults explain to them how to speak correctly.

So, if any of us is asked how a child learns the pronunciation, phonetics of his language, then most of us will say: imitating parents. Children, unlike us, talk, even with a meager vocabulary and having no idea about grammar, are not afraid to make mistakes and do not judge themselves for the mistakes they have made.

The absence of complexes helps children to immerse themselves in a foreign language without unnecessary baggage. Communicative approach is applied in much the same way: students discuss an interesting topic and learn to apply a new construction or vocabulary in the course of a conversation. For example, the teacher

explains the second type of conditional sentences and suggests talking about dreams: If I won much money, I would buy a Ferrari (If I won a lot of money, I would buy a Ferrari). After 5-10 sentences, students easily memorize this construction and understand the principles of its use. That is, grammar and vocabulary are not actually the main object of study, but are used as auxiliary material and learn automatically.

Life does not stand still, and the communicative methodology continues to develop. So, it began to be used in the individual form of training and in online lessons. Moreover, the communicative approach in English classes on Skype has its own distinctive features.

1. Individual approach. An individual approach means that the teacher adapts the training program to a specific student. After all, people differ from each other in their natural properties (abilities), and the ability to carry out educational and speech activities, and their characteristics as a person: personal experience, the context of activity, a set of certain feelings and emotions, interests, status (position) in the team. In English classes on Skype using a communicative method, all the teacher's attention is focused on only one student. This allows you to detect gaps in knowledge and quickly eliminate them. Thus, the student will not be too easy or too difficult in the classroom, he will have an incentive to develop, and at the same time he will thoroughly understand all the topics studied.

2. Students' choice of the volume and type of homework. It is worth noting that you can not completely abandon homework, since homework is the best way to fix the material in memory and check how well it is learned. Homework with a communicative approach is never boring – it can be online tests and crosswords, songs and various resources in English to test knowledge.

3. Using grammar and vocabulary as auxiliary material and learning them automatically. As in ordinary classroom classes, in online classes, students do not learn the dry wording of the rules. They learn the natural use of grammatical constructions and really useful words and expressions in practice.

4. Maximum practice in the classroom. For most of the lesson, students practice speaking. A few minutes are given to reading an interesting text, which

subsequently becomes a topic for discussion. Tasks to improve writing and listening skills are most often given at home. So, you can listen to the text or write a letter without hurrying, in a quiet environment. If something is unclear, the teacher will definitely come to the rescue and explain everything in class. This approach allows you to save time and work on the development of conversational speech, because this skill is usually the most difficult to master.

Thanks to this, the problem described at the beginning of the article is solved: "I understand everything, but I can't speak." The communicative methodology, despite the lack of "novelty" and "innovative approach", has many advantages. Today, this is undoubtedly the most effective way to learn English.

Thus, we can say with confidence: the communicative method of teaching English is suitable for absolutely everyone, and especially those who have had a not very pleasant experience of learning the language from ancient textbooks will appreciate it. The communicative technique is focused precisely on the possibility of communication. Of the four "whales" on which any language training (reading, writing, speaking and listening to speech), increased attention is paid to the latter two. Communicative method is designed primarily to remove the fear of communication. Communication is manifested in the functionality of learning. Functionality assumes that both words and grammatical forms are assimilated immediately in the activity, based on its execution. Based on the above, it can be concluded that communication is necessary in the learning process, since it serves to ensure that communication takes place in adequate conditions, such as taking into account the individuality of each student, the speech orientation of the learning process, the functionality of learning, situativeness communication, constant novelty of the learning process.

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